

Development and Optimization of a Multi-Label SVM for Chemogenomics

Georg Zitzlsberger^{a,*}, Vojtěch Cima^a^aIT4Innovations, VŠB - Technical University of Ostrava

Abstract

Support vector machine (SVM) based machine learning is used in a wide range of domains. It represents a family of supervised machine learning algorithms and is most commonly used for binary classification tasks. It can also be extended to multi-label problems which are specializations of multi-task classification. We use an early stage SVM implementation, called PermonSVM, to implement a one versus all multi-label method to classify and predict protein-compound activities in chemogenomics. The white paper highlights the VI-HPS tools Score-P, Cube and Vampir, as used during the early development and improvement processes of PermonSVM. We apply those tools to identify and analyze a bottleneck in the early PermonSVM implementation, and verify its final iteration.

1. Introduction

Supervised modeling is widely used in the pharmaceutical industry, especially during the early stage of drug design and development (DDD). Computational chemogenomics is a part of DDD and aims to predict protein-compound activities (targets) by reusing all available information to support current and prospective needs. On one hand, this significantly helps to reduce the cost, time and animal usage during the DDD process. On the other hand, the number of possible combinations grows with the addition of new targets or compounds, and scales beyond petascale levels for practical databases.

Chemogenomics aims to model biological activities between targeted chemical libraries of small molecules and individual drug target families (*e.g.* proteins) [1]. This, among other methods, can be achieved via multitask supervised methods such as matrix factorization or deep learning. Both of those methods are computationally very expensive and require domain knowledge expertise. Single-task models have an inherited limitation as they only capture binary context, and do not benefit from the transfer learning available in multitask methods. Yet, single-task methods can be converted into multitask methods via binarization (binary classification) techniques such as *one versus one* (OVO), or *one versus all* (OVA), which is also synonymously referred to as *one versus the rest*. Using a Support Vector Machine for such binary classifications is one possible solution.

In the following white paper we use the SVM implementation from the PERMON team¹ which is called PermonSVM [2]. Its implementation is, at the time of writing, in an early stage and under heavy development. We will be using a first prototype implementation of an OVA method developed by the PERMON team. The PermonSVM source code is available on Github [3].

Training data is made available by courtesy of the ExCAPE project [4]. We used their baseline *chem2vec* data set, which was used for the evaluation of different machine learning methods [5]. The data set is applied in a multi-label setup where the features of chemical compounds are related to chemogenomic targets (labels). The result is a multi-label model that allows the relating of features of various chemical compounds to a specific target.

The 27th VI-HPS Tuning Workshop [6] as offered by the Center of Excellence in HPC, Performance Optimisation (POP) [7], and organized by partners of PRACE, provided the tools and expert knowledge to apply the profiling and tracing tools. For performance analysis of PermonSVM, different VI-HPS tools [8], such as Score-P [9], Cube [10] and Vampir [11], are applied. We document the setup of Score-P for the PermonSVM software stack to retrieve profiling and tracing information and visualize them in Cube and Vampir, respectively.

PermonSVM and its software stack are described in section 2. Section 3 documents how we created PermonSVM enabled Score-P builds to collect profile and trace information. The actual profiling run and its key performance problem is discussed in section 4. Further on, tracing used for validation of the improvement

* Corresponding author e-mail: georg.zitzlsberger@vsb.cz, telephone: +420 597 329 560

¹David Horák, Marek Pecha, et al. <http://permon.vsb.cz/team.htm>

of PermonSVM is covered in section 5. Results of our work are shown in section 6 and a final conclusion in section 7.

2. PermonSVM Design

PermonSVM implements a non-linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a linear kernel² by using quadratic programming (QP) with boxed constraints. There are multiple variants of SVM [12] implementations, such as C -SVM, ν -SVM, ϵ -SVM or one-class SVM. PermonSVM is based on C -SVM, which allows a regularization parameter C . It has some impact on the number of support vectors used by the final model, with a higher value of C resulting in less support vectors and vice versa. Support vectors are a subset of the data points from the input, which are considered important enough to describe the resulting SVM model. The goal of using SVMs is to minimize the number of support vectors, which in turn results in a sparse representation of the input data points in the final model.

For a non-linear SVM, the problem is usually solved in the dual space, which is derived from the primal problem space as follows:

- Primal problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{w}, b, \xi} \quad & \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i=1}^l \xi_i \\ \text{subject to} \quad & y_i (\mathbf{w}^T \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \\ & \xi_i \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, l \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

- Dual problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \quad & \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^T Q \boldsymbol{\alpha} - \mathbf{e}^T \boldsymbol{\alpha} \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \mathbf{y}^T \boldsymbol{\alpha} = 0, \\ & 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C, i = 1, \dots, l \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The box constraint from the dual problem limits the range of weights for data points, with the upper bound defined by the parameter C . The vector $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ contains the weights of the input data represented by the Hessian Q , associated with their labels by the vector \mathbf{y} . Every element of $\alpha_i > 0$ defines a support vector that contributes to the (sparse) model. All other data points are ignored ($\alpha_i = 0$). The equality constraint results from the transformation to dual space.

The needed QP solver is not implemented by PermonSVM itself but makes use of PermonQP [13] (available on Github [14]). PermonQP provides solvers such as MPRGP [15] and SMALXE [16], which can be easily selected. However, different limitations apply:

- If SMALXE is used as the outermost solver, it requires an innermost solver, which is MPGRP [17] in our case. SMALXE asserts an equality constraint that MPGRP ignores, and the resulting SVM can be biased. However, this implementation is assumed to be slower in most cases due to the two nested solvers.
- If MPRGP is used merely as a solver, it does not support the equality constraint. It can be used however, by applying the no-bias version of SVM [18]. An extension of the feature dimensions is needed to compensate for the missing bias. Since this solver is not nested like SMALXE/MPGRP above, it is assumed to converge faster. However, moving the bias into the feature space could have side-effects due to its regularization.

In the following, we use the nested SMALXE/MPGRP solver setup and leave the analysis of the no-bias implementation to future work.

PermonQP implements different QP solvers and is based on PETSc [19] whose data types are used for the API. In turn, PermonSVM also uses PETSc for its data types and associated functions. The design of the PermonSVM solution illustrated in figure 1 puts the involved components into perspective. PETSc is the component that interfaces most with the MPI library to introduce parallelism. We ignore the non-computational interaction of PermonSVM with the MPI library, as for `MPI_Comm_rank(...)`, `MPI_Comm_size(...)`, *etc.*

PermonQP implements the solvers described above, which are used by the SVM to find the most suitable hyperplane that separates different classes/labels with the largest (soft-)margin. For the C -SVM this process is controlled by the parameter C which needs to be found empirically.

PermonSVM processes the training data grouped by labels (targets for compounds) and available as individual files in the *libsvm* file format. Since such file formats are not supported by PETSc, it is converted into a PETSc compatible matrix or vector format, which, to ease reuse, is written back to the storage. During training, PermonSVM creates a model which contains selected and weighted data points from the inputs (support vectors) plus a bias (offset). This model can be used for inference to predict unseen data, *i.e.* a set of chemical features to predict possible targets.

²Which makes it technically a linear SVM, but other non-linear kernels could be added in the same framework

Fig. 1. PermonSVM components and interactions. The training data set is converted from a *libsvm* to a PETSc format and stored on the file system for reuse. PermonSVM creates a model during the training process for future inference. PermonSVM is based on both PermonQP and PETSc, which in turn uses MPI for parallelism. Red arrows indicate interactions that are not needed for analyzing PermonSVM.

PETSc itself uses MPI to parallelize the computations, which utilizes the partition and distribution of data among the MPI processes. Arrows in red indicate layer APIs that are of no interest for PermonSVM analysis. Only interactions of PermonSVM with PermonQP and PETSc are the subject of our work. The other interactions, which are marked with red arrows in figure 1, are secondary.

3. Applying Score-P

Performance analysis of PermonSVM is required to understand the bottlenecks and provide improvements. Score-P can be used to extract detailed and precise (*i.e.* non-sampling) performance data. For PermonSVM, two approaches are possible; either instrumentation of the entire solution stack, or selective instrumentation of only the PermonSVM layer using library wrappers for calls to PermonQP and PETSc. In the following we explain both approaches in detail.

For both cases, we configured and compiled Score-P with the following commands, which adds support for profiling shared libraries, and uses the Intel C++/Fortran Compiler with Intel MPI:

```
$ configure --enable-shared --with-mpi=intel2 --with-nocross-compiler-suite=intel
↔ --prefix=<scorep_install_path> -with-qt-specs=linux-icc-64
$ make && make install
```

After completion, additional Score-P compiler wrappers must be created to support the Intel MPI compiler wrappers:

```
$ scorep-wrapper --create mpiicc
$ scorep-wrapper --create mpiicpc
$ scorep-wrapper --create mpiifort
```

3.1 Full Instrumentation with Score-P

Instrumentation of the entire software stack is the easiest approach. With a full instrumentation, detailed information about the internals of every layer is available. However, it requires a full recompilation with Score-P. In addition, with more information collected, the size of the profiling and tracing information also increases.

For the used software stack, the recompilation with Score-P is done in three sequential steps, ordered by the component dependencies:

1. PETSc:

First, the following environment variables need to be set:

```
$ export PETSC_DIR=<dir_to_petsc_sources>
$ export PETSC_ARCH=linux-gnu-intel
```

Then PETSc can be configured and built:

```
$ cd $PETSC_DIR
$ SCOREP_WRAPPER=off configure --with-cc=scorep-mpiicc --with-cxx=scorep-mpiicpc
  ↪ --with-fc=scorep-mpiifort --with-blas-lapack-dir=<path_to_mkl>/lib/intel64
  ↪ COPTFLAGS="-O3 -xHost -g" CXXOPTFLAGS="-O3 -xHost -g" FOPTFLAGS="-O3 -xHost
  ↪ -g"
$ make
```

The Score-P wrapper has to be turned off (`SCOREP_WRAPPER=off`) to not influence the PETSc build configuration tests. Hence, the Intel C++/Fortran compilers (using the Intel MPI wrappers like `mpiicpc`) are used directly.

2. PermonQP:

Subsequently, PermonQP is built using the same PETSc configuration. Similarly to PETSc, an environment variable is set to identify the source base before compilation:

```
$ export PERMON_DIR=<dir_to_permonqp_sources>
$ cd $PERMON_DIR
$ make
```

3. PermonSVM:

Finally, PermonSVM is built analogously to compile the SVM application:

```
$ export PERMON_SVM_DIR=<dir_to_permonsvm_sources>
$ cd $PERMON_SVM_DIR
$ make
```

The resulting PermonSVM executable, as well as the PETSc and PermonQP libraries, are Score-P instrumented versions. With every invocation of PermonSVM, it creates profile data in the current working directory. The amount of data collected includes all three layers. As already shown in figure 1, it also comprises information about PermonQP interacting with PETSc, and PETSc interacting with the MPI library, which are of no use in our case.

3.2 Selected Instrumentation with Score-P Library Wrappers

Instead of a full recompilation of the software stack with Score-P, a selective instrumentation can be used. Interfaces to non-instrumented layers can be covered by wrappers [20] which provide aggregated performance data for each API function. Advantages of this approach are not only a simplified recompilation, but also less profiling data of secondary interest being collected. A downside of this approach is the manual setup required for the wrapper functions.

Selected instrumentation follows the setup of the full instrumentation mentioned earlier, with the deviation that the build of PETSc and PermonQP should be invoked as follows:

```
$ SCOREP_WRAPPER=off make
```

This turns off Score-P for both libraries, which excludes them from instrumentation. Only PermonSVM is supposed to be built the regular way with the enabled Score-P wrapper (no `SCOREP_WRAPPER=off`). This results in a lack of information about which PETSc and PermonQP functions are called by PermonSVM. To still record them, a library wrapper for every function of interest is needed.

Manual creation of such library wrappers can be a tedious and time consuming task if the involved libraries have complex interfaces. This is especially true in our case, due to the large amount of functions that PETSc offers. In addition, further wrapper functions need to be created for PermonQP as well. To simplify this task, Score-P offers the tool `scorep-libwrap-init`. It creates a framework to implement the workflow for the creation of library wrappers. The workflow is depicted in figure 2. It mostly follows the following basic steps: i) add header files from the API for which we want to create wrapper functions, and a simple test case for the interface; ii) then build the test case and iteratively apply filters for functions (*i.e.* symbols) of no interest. The result is a set of wrapped functions which were derived from the APIs.

In our case, we initialized the library wrappers with the following command:

Fig. 2. Flow graph for the setup of Score-P library wrappers as described by [20]. The tool `scorep-libwrap-init` creates the wrapper with its own build system. Builds are issued by `make` and checks by `make check`. The wrapper is installed to Score-P with `make install`, and tested by `make installcheck`.

```

$ scorep-libwrap-init -x c++ --name filter_for_petsc_permonqp
↪ --display-name "Filter for PETSc and Permon (QP)"
↪ --cppflags "-I${PERMON_DIR}/include
↪             -I${PETSC_DIR}/include
↪             -I${PETSC_DIR}/${PETSC_ARCH}/include -O3 -xHost -g"
↪ --ldflags "-L${PETSC_DIR}/${PETSC_ARCH}/lib
↪            -L${PERMON_DIR}/${PETSC_ARCH}/lib/"
↪ --libs "-lpetsc -lpermon" --backend mpi --update
  
```

This initializes the library wrapper build framework with the description of PETSc and PermonQP header and library files, and the compiler options to use. The MPI backend is selected for awareness of the MPI compiler wrappers. The option `-update` is used so that subsequent calls only update the library wrapper framework and do not delete intermittent changes by the user. In our case, an additional modification had to be applied to the Makefile to extend `mpicxx` with the option `-cxx=icpc` to use the Intel C++ Compiler.

The library wrapper needs to cover the two interfaces to PermonQP and PETSc. We added their header files as used by PermonSVM to `libwrap.h` as created by the `scorep-libwrap-init` tool:

```

// PETSc:
#include <petsc/private/matimpl.h>
#include <petsc/private/petscimpl.h>
// Permon:
#include <permonqps.h>
#include <permon/private/qpsimpl.h>
  
```

Furthermore, we created a simple test case using the matrix vector multiplication from the PETSc library (function `MatMult(...)`)³. This is needed to generate code which uses the PETSc interface actively to validate the library wrapper functions in terms of symbol resolution (linking) and pre-filtering symbols of interest. Our first build with `make` failed, reporting the absence of a proper filter setup. A `make check` then extracted symbols that were either unused (file `missing.filter`) or were not resolved automatically (file `uncertain.filter`). In turn we created a file `filtered_permon.filter` which contained the paths to the headers, all symbols from the file `missing.filter` and a subset of symbols from the file `uncertain.filter` which was found empirically until `make` passed. An excerpt of the `filtered_permon.filter` file follows:

³Example: <https://www.mcs.anl.gov/petsc/petsc-current/src/ksp/ksp/examples/tutorials/ex1.c.html>

```

SCOREP_FILE_NAMES_BEGIN
  INCLUDE <path_to>/permon/include/*
  INCLUDE <path_to>/petsc-3.9.4/include/*
  INCLUDE <path_to>/petsc-3.9.4/linux-gnu-intel/include/*
SCOREP_FILE_NAMES_END
SCOREP_REGION_NAMES_BEGIN
  # from missing.filter (all)
  EXCLUDE MANGLED _ZNSt9exceptionC2Ev
  EXCLUDE MANGLED _ZNSt9exceptionC1Ev
  ...
  # from uncertain.filter (selected)
  EXCLUDE MANGLED sigaction
  EXCLUDE MANGLED sigstack
  EXCLUDE MANGLED matherr
  ...
SCOREP_REGION_NAMES_END

```

It is known [20] that in some cases types cannot be fully resolved. This was also true for our use case, which involved the structures `stat` and `stat64`. It was trivial to solve by adding the full type definition `struct stat` and `struct stat64`, respectively, to two files created by `make`: `scorep_libwrap_filtered_permon.cc` and `scorep_libwrap_filtered_permon.inc.c`.

After the build passes its own tests, the filter can be installed with `make install`. A final `make installcheck` validates the installed filter. The filter is installed into Score-P's installation directory which hence becomes globally available. Once the library wrapper is available, PermonSVM can be compiled with it:

```

$ SCOREP_WRAPPER_INSTRUMENTER_FLAGS="--libwrap=filter_for_petsc_permonqp"
↪ SCOREP_WRAPPER=on make

```

This enables the Score-P compiler, and adds the library wrapper `filter_for_petsc_permonqp` to record PermonQP and PETSc functions. PermonSVM itself is compiled with full instrumentation.

3.3 Selection of Score-P Enabled Builds

Enabling a build with Score-P introduces runtime overhead for the profiled and traced application. For cases of benchmarking the application performance, or for production use, such an instrumentation is unwanted. Only for analysis runs, Score-P enabled applications are of interest.

For our setup we can use the environment `PETSC_ARCH` to switch between instrumented and production build. The environment variable is part of the PETSc build system and allows parallel builds for different architectures. We extend the definition of architecture by differentiating between Score-P enabled and production builds, *e.g.*:

- `PETSC_ARCH=linux-gnu-intel` with Score-P instrumentation
- `PETSC_ARCH=linux-gnu-intel_prod` without Score-P instrumentation

The former is used as above, to provide a Score-P enabled PermonSVM. The latter can be used to build the PETSc/PermonQP/PermonSVM stack with `SCOREP_WRAPPER=off` in call cases. This creates two software stacks, which can be used interchangeably.

The Score-P enabled build of PermonSVM stores the profiling information in a subdirectory. This subdirectory follows the naming convention `scorep-<date>_<time>_<value>` with date and time stamps. An individual value is added to avoid collisions in case multiple applications are invoked at the same time, which can be likely for MPI processes on different nodes. The default location of the subdirectory is the local working directory, and can be changed by the environment variable `SCOREP_EXPERIMENT_DIRECTORY`.

4. Profiling PermonSVM

PermonSVM is used in a multi-label classification setup to apply it to the *chem2vec* reference baseline from the ExCAPE project. The selected multi-label OVA method classifies each label (class) individually against all other labels (other classes). The result is a set of n models, with n being the number of different labels (*i.e.* targets). This is different to pairwise classification such as one versus one (OVO) which results in $(n^2 - n)/2$ models. We only consider OVA at the start but also anticipate OVO with its significantly increased amount of classifications for future versions.

The format of the input data for each OVA iteration is the full data set with labels being replaced with $+1$ when positive and -1 otherwise. The original data set has a size of approximately 900 MB, which is specialized n times. The *chem2vec* baseline has 7354 different labels, which would require over 7 TB of storage to keep the different data sets. As persistent storage would not be required, this data could be created on the fly.

What is more, early analysis with a limited workload containing only two labels shows that over 75% of the execution time is spent loading the data. Figure 3 shows the profiling data of PermonSVM instrumented with Score-P and visualized in Cube. The highlighted function `svm_file_load(...)` not only loads the data set, but also converts it to a PETSc compatible format (types `Mat` and `Vec`) and stores it back on the file system for reuse by subsequent runs. Only 25% of the runtime is spent training the SVM (function `PermonSVMTrain(...)`).

Since most of the data for the individual classifications is redundant, we changed the data format. First, PermonSVM loads the data file that contains the features only once, and outsources the label descriptions for each individual classification to its own file. The label files are loaded for every classification whilst the features are kept in memory. The feature file still has a size of 900 MB, but the label files are less than 70 kB each. This reduces the overall storage requirements from over 7 TB down to $900 \text{ MB} + 7354 * 70 \text{ kB} \approx 1.5 \text{ GB}$. Roughly twice that space is needed for storing the PETSc converted data files. This can be further reduced if reuse of the feature and label data is not needed.

With the improvement in place, the profile data shows the expected balance shift from data conversion to training. The function `svm_file_load(...)` now only uses up to 55% of the runtime and the SVM training is now up to 45%, with the entire runtime reduced by 30%. Figure 4 shows the profile information with the improved input file handling. Again, this was the same simplified two label scenario used above. The reduction of redundant data conversion (and storage) grows with more labels being processed (up to 7354 from *chem2vec*).

5. Tracing PermonSVM

The profile information shown by Cube is useful for spotting bottlenecks. However, it does not provide any additional timeline context. This is possible with tracing data, which contains more information compared to profile data, as we have used so far. Traces collect events, such as function invocations from the MPI library or user code, and assigns timestamps to them. Additional annotations to events are possible, such as MPI node or rank, or CPU core associated with an event.

5.1 Applying Filters

Trace files can grow significantly large (over TBs even for short runtimes). Such huge trace files are rendered unusable in practical terms as they would not only occupy large amounts of file system space, but also additional CPU memory, needed for the accounting of events. For the PermonSVM project, the memory and storage requirements can be retrieved with the `scorep-score` command. Listing 1 shows an example of this command and its output.

The required storage for the trace file is highlighted in red (70 GB). We used the same two label examples as before, which results in a PermonSVM run for 8156.52 CPU seconds. Longer runs would need proportionally more space. The minimum main memory size is highlighted in green (4 GB) and is needed to keep track of all events. Whilst the main memory requirements are acceptable, the storage needs are far from practical.

The output also shows the contributors to the trace data by size (column `max_buf`). As can be seen, low level library functions take up most of the storage space. Two are highlighted in blue with 7.3 GiB and 3.4 GiB size. Analysis shows that for the majority of functions among the top storage consumers, trace data are not needed, and can be filtered out. Also, such candidates follow similar patterns to the same low level libraries. As a solution, a filter is applied to avoid unnecessary data collection. Since patterns recur, the filter (`psvm.flt`) is rather simple:

```
SCOREP_REGION_NAMES_BEGIN EXCLUDE
*std:**
*__gnu*
*__gnu_cxx:**
atoi
operator?new
```

Rerunning the `scorep-score` tool now shows a significantly minimized trace storage requirement, as seen in the listing 2. The overall storage requirement is now down to 630 MB with only 362 MB of main memory being needed. This makes tracing practical and also speeds up the execution of the traced PermonSVM due to lowered overhead.

5.2 Collecting and Analyzing Trace Information with Vampir

With the filter in place, PermonSVM can now be traced. For that, it is invoked with additional environment variables:

- `SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY`: Specifies how much memory to allocate for accounting of trace information. The value can be taken directly from the `scorep-score` report.

Selected "svm_file_load_binary"

Fig. 3. Profile visualization of the original PermonSVM OVA implementation with Cube. The selected metric is time (in CPU seconds) with the hottest functions highlighted (75% of combined CPU time).

Selected "svm_file_convert_X"

Fig. 4. Profile visualization of the improved PermonSVM OVA implementation with Cube. The selected metric is time (in CPU seconds) with the hottest functions highlighted (55% of combined CPU time).

Listing 1. Invocation of `scorep-score` showing the memory (highlighted green) and storage (highlighted red) requirements of PermonSVM without filters applied. Highlights in blue show the individual storage requirements of non-relevant regions.

```
$ scorep-score -r scorep-result_improved/profile.cubex
```

Estimated aggregate size of event trace: 70GB
 Estimated requirements for largest trace buffer (max_buf): 70GB
 Estimated memory requirements (SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY): 70GB
 (warning: The memory requirements cannot be satisfied by Score-P to avoid intermediate flushes when tracing. Set SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY=4G to get the maximum supported memory or reduce requirements using USR regions filters.)

flt	type	max_buf [B]	visits	time [s]	time [%]	time/visit [us]	region
	ALL	74,149,802,023	2,859,906,065	5761.78	100.0	2.01	ALL
	USR	74,055,395,582	2,849,940,890	777.40	13.5	0.27	USR
	MPI	94,405,401	9,965,024	3068.20	53.3	307.90	MPI
	COM	1,040	151	1916.18	33.3	12689905.02	COM
	USR	7,292,888,070	280,496,055	38.79	0.7	0.14	
		std::__cxx11::basic_string<char, std::char_traits<char>, std::allocator<char> >::_M_data					
	USR	3,386,070,064	130,233,740	24.66	0.4	0.19	
		__gnu_cxx::new_allocator<char>::new_allocator					
...							

Listing 2. Invocation of `scorep-score` showing the memory and storage requirements of PermonSVM with filters applied. Filtered regions are marked with either + (full) or * (partial), and unfiltered are marked with - in the `flt` column.

```
$ scorep-score -f psvm.flt -r scorep-result_improved/profile.cubex
```

Estimated aggregate size of event trace: 630MB
 Estimated requirements for largest trace buffer (max_buf): 360MB
 Estimated memory requirements (SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY): 362MB
 (hint: When tracing set SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY=362MB to avoid intermediate flushes or reduce requirements using USR regions filters.)

flt	type	max_buf [B]	visits	time [s]	time [%]	time/visit [us]	region
-	ALL	74,149,802,023	2,859,906,065	5761.78	100.0	2.01	ALL
-	USR	74,055,395,582	2,849,940,890	777.40	13.5	0.27	USR
-	MPI	94,405,401	9,965,024	3068.20	53.3	307.90	MPI
-	COM	1,040	151	1916.18	33.3	12689905.02	COM
*	ALL	376,783,003	20,825,941	5024.26	87.2	241.25	ALL -FLT
+	FLT	73,773,019,020	2,839,080,124	737.51	12.8	0.26	FLT
*	USR	282,376,562	10,860,766	39.89	0.7	3.67	USR -FLT
-	MPI	94,405,401	9,965,024	3068.20	53.3	307.90	MPI -FLT
*	COM	1,040	151	1916.18	33.3	12689905.02	COM -FLT
+	USR	7,292,888,070	280,496,055	38.79	0.7	0.14	
		std::__cxx11::basic_string<char, std::char_traits<char>, std::allocator<char> >::_M_data					
+	USR	3,386,070,064	130,233,740	24.66	0.4	0.19	
		__gnu_cxx::new_allocator<char>::new_allocator					
...							

Fig. 5. Visualization of Score-P traces with Vampir. The Timing differences between the original and improved (blue background) versions are visible in the timeline view, demonstrating improved parallelization and shorter time to solution.

- `SCOREP_ENABLE_TRACING=true`:
Enables tracing in addition to profiling. By default this is off.
- `SCOREP_FILTERING_FILE`:
Uses the specified filter file to minimize the tracing data.

The following shows an example of how to retrieve trace information by invoking PermonSVM (`permonsvmfile`) with an OVA multi-label classification and a fixed parameter C on 24 MPI ranks:

```
$ SCOREP_TOTAL_MEMORY=362MB SCOREP_ENABLE_TRACING=true SCOREP_FILTERING_FILE=psvm.flt
↪ SCOREP_EXPERIMENT_DIRECTORY=scorep-result-improved
↪ mpirun -n 24 ../linux-gnu-intel/bin/permonsvmfile -multiclass ova
↪ -f_list_train list_of_files_to_train.txt -svm_C 0.1
```

Once PermonSVM finishes, the result directory (`scorep-result-improved`) contains tracing information in addition to the profile data. The trace files can be inspected with the Vampir tool. We use the compare feature from Vampir to analyze differences between the two PermonSVM versions discussed in section 4. For this, we created traces within the same environment for both versions with 24 MPI ranks. An example is shown in figure 5. The improved PermonSVM version is displayed with a blue background, and shows a reduced wall time due to the reduced file conversion overhead. The file conversions in both cases are easy to recognize since only the first rank is processing while all other ranks are blocked (`MPI_Barrier`). Again, this example only uses two labels for demonstration purposes.

6. Results

The results of our work are based on an interim version of PermonSVM, which is under heavy development at the time of writing. We started with an early OVA implementation in PermonSVM to implement a multi-label classification. This classification setup has been used with the *chem2vec* baseline data from the ExCAPE project to create a model that allows us to relate features of various chemical compounds to a specific target.

The previous results were collected on a development system, and only used the two labels with the most data points. As *chem2vec* consists of 7354 labels we also analyzed the strong scaling of both PermonSVM versions on a single node⁴. For this, we used all labels with more than 600 data points (approximately 30% of the entire data set) for training with a fixed hyperparameter $C = 0.1$. Strong scaling results are shown in figure 6 and indicate the speedup saturating around 30%, with a good strong scaling up to 8 MPI ranks. This stems from the minimized memory and storage footprint with the reduced file I/O and data conversion. The given workload is not able to utilize more parallelism. Adding the remaining labels does not improve the situation,

⁴The node is a two socket Intel Xeon E5-2680v3, 2.5 GHz, 12 cores each

Fig. 6. Runtimes between original and improved PermonSVM ($C = 0.1$), scaled up to 24 MPI ranks (CPU cores of one node). The speedup of the improved version is plotted in relation to the original version, which saturates around 30%. The largest 30% of labels from the *chem2vec* dataset were used.

because less data points per label result in a reduced solver time. The runtime is then dominated by the file conversion and storage which works stronger against the parallelization.

Furthermore, we applied the VI-HPS tools for analysis and verification. The tools used were Score-P, Cube and Vampir, being applied to the complex PermonSVM software stack. PermonQP and PETSc are part of this software stack and add challenges for analysis since only their interactions with PermonSVM are of interest.

We used Score-P to collect profiling information in two ways. First, we analyzed the entire software stack, which is the easiest solution. Second, we narrowed down analysis to PermonSVM using library wrappers, which allows selective profiling. The setup of the library wrappers for PermonQP and PETSc has been described.

Visualization of the original PermonSVM implementation’s profiling data with Cube unveiled a hot spot in the data conversion when loading the training data. We applied an improvement to reduce this overhead, both for runtime and storage, for a better time to solution.

Finally, both PermonSVM versions were traced with Score-P and visualized with Vampir. Given the size of the trace files, we documented our approach to reducing storage and memory requirements by applying a filter. The filter was balanced to retain the most important tracing information for PermonSVM, its parallelization and (MPI) synchronization.

7. Conclusion

We have improved the PermonSVM implementation for a multi-label OVA classification of a real data set from the ExCAPE project. The application of different VI-HPS tools helped us to analyze and validate the PermonSVM performance characteristics. As described, the complexity of the PermonSVM software stack requires additional preparation to apply these tools, which we documented. The results of the tools delivered a consistent picture of the different PermonSVM implementations, and guided our development and optimization processes.

What is more, hyper-parameter search and cross-validation schemes widely used in ExCAPE would result in a high number of independent single-node tasks. These can be processed in large-scale systems in a distributed fashion using computational frameworks such as HyperLoom [21]. As this approach relies on multiple instantiations of the same application (varying parametrization and/or data), the efficiency of the whole computation highly depends on the efficiency of the application itself. This has been demonstrated in the ExCAPE project to be a candidate for exascale systems. Whilst ExCAPE used *scikit-learn* SVM, which in turn uses *libsvm* internally, PermonSVM could be used as a replacement in ExCAPE’s HyperLoom framework. The current results of PermonSVM for the *chem2vec* data set suggests the use of 8 MPI ranks for the training, with a fixed set of hyperparameters (C for C -SVM) for the best efficiency. Analyzing a large range of C can scale beyond petascale systems, especially once larger datasets than *chem2vec* are used.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 730913. We would also like to acknowledge partners in the ExCAPE project providing us with the *chem2vec* dataset and the POP project in offering the VI-HPS Tuning Workshops.

References

1. M. Bredel and E. Jacoby, “Chemogenomics: an emerging strategy for rapid target and drug discovery,” *Nature Reviews Genetics*, vol. 5, no. 4, p. 262, 2004.
2. PERMON Team, “PermonSVM,” <http://permon.vsb.cz/permonsvm.htm>, accessed 2019-02-01.
3. —, “PermonSVM - the Permon SVM classifier,” <https://github.com/permon/permonsvm>, accessed 2019-02-01.
4. “Excape: Exascale compound activity prediction,” <http://www.excape-h2020.eu/>, accessed 2019-02-01.
5. ExCAPE, “Public deliverables,” <http://www.excape-h2020.eu/index.php/documents>, accessed 2019-02-01.
6. “27th VI-HPS Tuning Workshop (LRZ, Garching, Germany),” <https://www.vi-hps.org/training/tws/tw27.html>, accessed 2019-02-01.
7. “Performance Optimisation and Productivity (POP),” <https://pop-coe.eu/>, accessed 2019-02-01.
8. “Virtual institute - high productivity supercomputing,” <https://www.vi-hps.org/>, accessed 2019-02-01.
9. “VI-HPS: Scalable Performance Measurement Infrastructure for Parallel Codes (Score-P),” <https://www.vi-hps.org/projects/score-p/>, accessed 2019-02-01.
10. “VI-HPS: Cube,” <https://www.vi-hps.org/tools/cube.html>, accessed 2019-02-01.
11. “VI-HPS: Vampir,” <https://www.vi-hps.org/tools/vampir.html>, accessed 2019-02-01.
12. C.-C. Chang and C.-J. Lin, “LIBSVM: A library for support vector machines,” *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology*, vol. 2, pp. 27:1–27:27, 2011, software available at <http://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/libsvm>.
13. PERMON Team, “PermonQP,” <http://permon.vsb.cz/permonqp.htm>, accessed 2019-02-01.
14. —, “Permon toolbox,” <https://github.com/permon/permon>, accessed 2019-02-01.
15. Z. Dostál, T. Kozubek, M. Sadowska, and V. Vondrák, *Scalable Algorithms for Contact Problems*, ser. Advances in Mechanics and Mathematics. Springer-Verlag New York, 2016, vol. 36.
16. V. Hapla, “Massively parallel quadratic programming solvers with applications in mechanics,” Ph.D. dissertation, VŠB - Technical University of Ostrava, 2016.
17. J. Kružík, M. Pecha, V. Hapla, D. Horák, and M. Čermák, “Investigating convergence of linear svm implemented in permonsvm employing mprgp algorithm,” in *High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering*, T. Kozubek, M. Čermák, P. Tichý, R. Blaheta, J. Šístek, D. Lukáš, and J. Jaroš, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 115–129.
18. C.-J. Hsieh, K.-W. Chang, C.-J. Lin, S. S. Keerthi, and S. Sundararajan, “A dual coordinate descent method for large-scale linear svm,” in *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Machine Learning*, ser. ICML '08. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2008, pp. 408–415. [Online]. Available: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1390156.1390208>
19. PETSc Team, “Portable, extensible toolkit for scientific computation,” <https://www.mcs.anl.gov/petsc/>, accessed 2019-02-01.
20. R. Brendel, B. Wesarg, R. Tschüter, M. Weber, T. Ilsche, and S. Oeste, “Generic library interception for improved performance measurement and insight,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1803.07495, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1803.07495>
21. V. Cima, S. Böhm, J. Martinovič, J. Dvorský, K. Janurová, T. V. Aa, T. J. Ashby, and V. Chupakhin, “Hyperloom: A platform for defining and executing scientific pipelines in distributed environments,” in *Proceedings of the 9th Workshop and 7th Workshop on Parallel Programming and RunTime Management Techniques for Manycore Architectures and Design Tools and Architectures for Multicore Embedded Computing Platforms*. ACM, 2018, pp. 1–6.